

References

1. V. V. YBOLK, A. D. LANGADE and V. M. SHINDE, *Mikrochim. Acta*, in press.
2. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Nankodo, Tokyo, 1964, p. 51.
3. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 179.
4. N. J. PATIL and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 1037.

Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II) Phenylacetate Complexes with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THORNTON *et al.* have reported¹ some Ni^{II} complexes of benzoates and substituted benzoates with heterocyclic amine ligands. More recently Guru *et al.* have also reported² some phenylacetate complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with nitrogen donor ligands. In the present communication we report some mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} and Zn^{II} phenylacetates with different nitrogen donor ligands.

Experimental

Ethanolic solutions of Zn^{II} and Co^{II} phenylacetates were mixed with different nitrogen donor ligands in stoichiometric ratio and the resulting solutions were refluxed on water bath for 2 h. The 2,2'-dipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline complexes separated out on shaking and cooling, while the pyridine and γ -picoline complexes were obtained after keeping the solution for more than 24 h. The complexes were filtered under suction, washed with

ethanol and ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes of zinc are white crystalline solid and those of cobalt are pink crystalline and have the composition ML₂B₂ or ML₂B', where B=pyridine and γ -picoline and B'=2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline. The compounds are soluble in acetone in which medium they behave as non-electrolyte, as the Δ_M values are low being 9 to 15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ (Table 1). All the cobalt(II) compounds are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values 4.9 to 5.1 B.M. indicating the octahedral stereochemistry. The high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes have³ large orbital contributions to spin only values and the magnetic moments are found to vary from 4.7 to 5.2 B.M. The high orbital contribution is attributable to the three-fold orbital degeneracy of the ⁴T_{1g} ground state.

In free sodium phenylacetate asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching frequencies appear at 1610 and 1400 cm⁻¹, respectively⁴. In metal phenylacetates these bands appear slightly to a lower frequency region, but again shifts to higher frequency region in case of mixed ligand complexes indicating that both phenylacetate and the nitrogen donor ligands are bonded to the metal ion. Further, most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands are also modified indicating⁵ their coordination to the metal ion. The far ir spectra of the three complexes exhibit two bands at $\sim 350 \nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\sim 250 \text{ cm}^{-1} \nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$. These bands further confirm that both phenylacetate and nitrogen donor ligands are bonded to the metal ion. The difference between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ mode of complexes are of the order 210-220 cm⁻¹ indicating the bidentate nature of the phenylacetate as this difference will be of higher order for monodentate acetate group.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour and form	Δ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
				M	N
CoL ₂ (Py) ₂	Pink crystalline	9.5	4.80	12.00 (12.04)	5.68 (5.72)
CoL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	Pink crystalline	10.0	5.10	11.32 (11.40)	5.40 (5.44)
CoL ₂ (2,2'-Dipy)	Pink crystalline	11.2	4.96	11.97 (12.04)	5.65 (5.72)
CoL ₂ (1,10-Phen)	Rosy crystalline	11.8	4.96	11.92 (11.56)	5.47 (5.49)
ZnL ₂ (Py) ₂	White crystalline	13.0	—	13.10 (13.18)	5.60 (5.65)
ZnL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	White crystalline	14.5	—	12.45 (12.54)	5.30 (5.37)
ZnL ₂ (2,2'-Dipy)	White crystalline	14.0	—	13.05 (13.18)	5.60 (5.65)
ZnL ₂ (1,10-Phen)	White crystalline	13.8	—	12.60 (12.67)	5.38 (5.42)

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Cobalt(II) complexes give rise to two bands around 18,000 and 20,000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition characteristic of octahedral Co^{II} ion in O_h symmetry^{3,6}. Electronic spectra and μ_{eff} values are in conformity with the high spin octahedral configuration of cobalt(II) complexes.

Infrared spectral data indicate that zinc complexes have an octahedral environment around the metal ion involving bidentate acetate group and the nitrogen donor ligands.

References

1. J. CATTERICK and P. THORNTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 233.
2. C. D. RAO, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 631.
3. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1969, p. 870.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrophotometric Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1967.
5. J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibration of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1977.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.

Complexing Behaviour of Some New Schiff Bases: High Spin Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with Tridentate and Tetradentate Schiff Base Ligands

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THE synthesis, structural investigations and reactions of metal chelates with sulphur containing Schiff's bases have received renewed attention in recent years because of their proven antitumour^{1,2} and carcinostatic activities^{3,4}. Coordination compounds of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with various Schiff bases have been studied extensively⁵⁻⁸ but little is known about the complexes of Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic glyoxalic aldehydes. Hence, an attempt has been made here to prepare and characterise nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chelates with Schiff bases derived from 2-acetyl thiophene glyoxal and various amines.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. 2-Acetyl thiophene glyoxal was prepared by the reported method⁹. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of 2-acetyl thiophene glyoxal with *p*-aminobenzoic acid, *p*-toluidine, 2-aminopyridine and *o*-phenylenediamine in absolute ethanol. These

were purified by recrystallisation from absolute ethanol. Complexes were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of ligands and metal chlorides in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1-4 h and then concentrated to a small volume. On cooling, crystals of the complexes obtained were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air.

The analyses of carbon and hydrogen were done at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Metals were estimated by Vogel's method¹⁰ after decomposing the complex with a mixture of H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 . Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method at room temperature (288 K) using water as calibrant. Dimagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants. Electronic spectra were recorded in acetone on Toshniwal visible spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer model 621 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complexes under investigation are listed in Table 1 along with their colour, analysis and other properties. Analytical data of these complexes reveal 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The molar conductance values (3.78-12.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in acetone solution adequately confirm the non-ionic nature of the complexes¹¹. The magnetic moments of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are in the ranges 4.65-5.05 and 2.98-3.25 B.M., respectively indicating the spin-free octahedral geometry around the metal ions¹².

The cobalt(II) complexes show two d-d bands in 15151-16260 and 18181-19610 cm^{-1} regions which may be attributed to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, respectively. ν_1 was not observed due to instrumental limitation. ν_1 was calculated by the method (C)¹³ using the calculated values of 10 Dq and B (Table 2).

The values of transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 may be obtained by Konig's equations^{14,15}. The ligand field parameter B and the ligand field splitting energy (10 Dq) in case of cobalt(II) complexes were calculated¹⁶. Out of the four methods applicable in case of Cobalt(II) complexes, the best fitting method is 13C because the ratio $\nu_2(\text{obs})/\nu_1(\text{calcd.})$ is found to be around 2.14-2.15 as required for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes, and the calculated values of 10Dq is in good agreement to that determined by $\nu_2(\text{obs}) - \nu_1(\text{calcd.})$. The values of β of these complexes are between 0.5-1.0 and clearly indicate the partial covalent character of the bond concerned. However, the electronic spectral data suggest octahedral geometry for all the complexes¹⁷.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes (Table 3) are consistent with their octahedral geometry showing three d-d transition bands in 10526-11364, 16129-17241 and 25000-27777 cm^{-1} regions